

FAMILIES OF NON-CONGRUENT NUMBERS WITH ARBITRARILY MANY PAIRS OF PRIME FACTORS

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Abstract

In this article we show the existence of infinitely many new families, each containing infinitely many non-congruent numbers. These non-congruent numbers are obtained as products of an arbitrary number of pairs of primes (p_j, q_j) , all of which are equivalent either to $(1, 3)$ or to $(5, 7)$ modulo 8.

1. Introduction

A natural number n is called a congruent number if it is the area of a right triangle with rational lengths. Equivalently, n is a non-congruent number if the elliptic curve

$$E_n : y^2 = x^3 - n^2x \tag{1}$$

has Mordell-Weil rank 0, i.e., Equation (1) has no rational solution other than the four 2-torsion points $(0, 0)$, $(\pm n, 0)$ and the point \mathcal{O} at infinity on E_n . The elliptic curve E_n is referred to as the *congruent number elliptic curve*. Without loss of generality, we shall restrict our attention to square-free natural numbers n throughout this article. To determine all congruent and non-congruent numbers is one of the long-standing problems in number theory. The Birch and Swinnerton-Dyer Conjecture for a rational elliptic curve predicts that a square-free natural number n is congruent if $n \equiv 5, 6$ or $7 \pmod{8}$. Tunnel [9], Monsky [4] and Tian [8]

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are some of the eminent mathematicians who have made significant contributions toward identifying congruent numbers. For the known results on the construction of non-congruent numbers with arbitrarily many prime factors of the form $8k + 3$, one can refer to [2] and [5] for instance.

In [3], Lagrange proved that a composite number of the form pq must be non-congruent when p and q are primes with $\left(\frac{p}{q}\right) = -1$ and $(p, q) \equiv (1, 3)$ or $(5, 7) \pmod{8}$. Serf ([6]) proved that a composite number of the form $(p_1q_1)(p_2q_2)$ must be non-congruent where the prime factors $p_1, p_2 \equiv 5 \pmod{8}$ and $q_1, q_2 \equiv 7 \pmod{8}$ with certain conditions on the associated Legendre symbols. In this article we show the existence of infinitely many new families of composite non-congruent numbers, obtained as products of arbitrary numbers of pairs of primes (p_j, q_j) , all of which are equivalent either to $(1, 3)$ or to $(5, 7)$ modulo 8. The main result of this article can be stated as follows.

Theorem 1. *Let t be a positive integer. Suppose p_1, p_2, \dots, p_t and q_1, q_2, \dots, q_t are distinct primes such that all pairs (p_j, q_j) are equivalent either to $(1, 3)$ or to $(5, 7)$ modulo 8. Suppose*

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{q_j}{q_i}\right) &= -1 \quad \text{if } i > j, & \left(\frac{p_i}{p_j}\right) &= 1 \quad \text{if } i \neq j, \quad \text{and} \\ \left(\frac{p_i}{q_j}\right) &= \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } i \neq j \\ -1 & \text{if } i = j, \end{cases} \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

where (\cdot) denotes the Legendre symbol. Then

$$n = (p_1q_1)(p_2q_2) \cdots (p_tq_t)$$

is a non-congruent number.

The following theorem guarantees that for each positive integer t , we do have infinitely many pairs of primes $(p_1, q_1), \dots, (p_t, q_t)$ satisfying the conditions of Theorem 1.

Theorem 2. *Let H_t denote the collection of positive integers with prime factorization $(p_1q_1)(p_2q_2) \cdots (p_tq_t)$, where all the pairs (p_j, q_j) are equivalent to $(1, 3)$ modulo 8 and satisfy the conditions (2). For any natural number t , the set H_t contains infinitely many elements. The analogous statement for pairs $(p_j, q_j) \equiv (5, 7) \pmod{8}$ holds as well.*

The method of complete 2-descent is a convenient tool in computing Mordell-Weil rank of an elliptic curve (see [8]). In Section 2, we briefly discuss how 2-descent leads to an ‘unsolvability condition’ for ruling out existence of non-torsion rational points on E_n (see Corollary 1). In Section 3, we show that the unsolvability condition holds for composite numbers of the form given in Theorem 1. Finally, we show in Section

4 that Theorem 1 provides infinitely many families, each containing infinitely many non-congruent numbers. We furnish a few examples of non-congruent numbers to illustrate our results.

2. An Unsolvability Condition

In this section we first recall the key aspects of the method of complete 2-descent that we need. Then we state an ‘unsolvability condition’ for the Mordell-Weil group $E_n(\mathbb{Q})$ to have rank zero, which rules out additional rational points on E_n . The method of 2-descent is an algorithm used for computing the rank of an elliptic curve. For elliptic curves given by the general Weierstrass equation $y^2 = (x - e_1)(x - e_2)(x - e_3)$ with $e_1, e_2, e_3 \in K$, where K is a number field, the process involved in carrying out the method of complete 2-descent is described in Proposition 1.4 on page 315 of [7]. For curves of the form, $y^2 = x(x^2 - n^2)$ the procedure can be summarized by the following proposition (see [6]).

Proposition 1 (Complete 2-Descent). *Let*

$$n = 2^\epsilon r_1 r_2 \cdots r_k$$

be a square-free positive integer where $\epsilon \in \{0, 1\}$, k is a natural number, and r_1, r_2, \dots, r_k are odd primes. Let E_n be the elliptic curve over \mathbb{Q} defined by

$$E_n : y^2 = x(x - n)(x + n),$$

and

$$S = \{\infty, 2, r_1, r_2, \dots, r_k\}$$

be a finite subset of $M_{\mathbb{Q}}$, the set of all places of \mathbb{Q} . In addition, define

$$\mathbb{Q}(S, 2) := \{c \in \mathbb{Q}^*/(\mathbb{Q}^*)^2 \mid \nu_p(c) \equiv 0 \pmod{2} \quad \forall p \in M_{\mathbb{Q}} \setminus S\},$$

where $\nu_p(c)$ is the p -adic valuation of c . Then there exists an injective homomorphism

$$b : E_n(\mathbb{Q})/2E_n(\mathbb{Q}) \hookrightarrow \mathbb{Q}(S, 2) \times \mathbb{Q}(S, 2) \tag{3}$$

defined by

$$P = (x, y) \longmapsto \begin{cases} (1, 1), & \text{if } P = \mathcal{O} \\ (-1, -n), & \text{if } P = (0, 0) \\ (n, 2), & \text{if } P = (n, 0) \\ (x, x - n), & \text{if } P \neq \mathcal{O}, (0, 0), (n, 0). \end{cases}$$

If $(b_1, b_2) \in \mathbb{Q}(S, 2) \times \mathbb{Q}(S, 2) \setminus \text{Im}\{\mathcal{O}, (0, 0), (\pm n, 0)\}$, then $(b_1, b_2) \in \text{Im}(b)$ if and only if there exist $(z_1, z_2, z_3) \in \mathbb{Q}^ \times \mathbb{Q}^* \times \mathbb{Q}^*$ such that the following two equations simultaneously hold:*

$$b_1 z_1^2 - b_2 z_2^2 = n, \tag{4}$$

$$b_1z_1^2 - b_1b_2z_3^2 = -n. \tag{5}$$

In this case, $(b_1, b_2) = b(P)$ for $P = (b_1z_1^2, b_1b_2z_1z_2z_3)$.

Remark 1. A system of representatives of classes in $\mathbb{Q}(S, 2)$ is given by

$$R = \{(-1)^\alpha 2^\beta r_1^{\epsilon_1} \cdots r_k^{\epsilon_k} \mid \alpha, \beta, \epsilon_1, \dots, \epsilon_k = 0 \text{ or } 1\}.$$

Let r be the rank of the Mordell-weil group $E_n(\mathbb{Q})$ of rational points on the elliptic curve E_n . Then $E_n(\mathbb{Q})$ is isomorphic to $\mathbb{Z}/2\mathbb{Z} \oplus \mathbb{Z}/2\mathbb{Z} \oplus \mathbb{Z}^r$, and consequently,

$$E_n(\mathbb{Q})/2E_n(\mathbb{Q}) \cong (\mathbb{Z}/2\mathbb{Z})^{r+2}.$$

For n to be a non-congruent number, we require that $r = 0$. In other words, we need to show that the system of equations given by (4) and (5) does not have a solution for any pair

$$(b_1, b_2) \in R \times R \setminus \{(1, 1), (-1, -n), (n, 2), (-n, -2n)\}. \tag{6}$$

The following proposition rules out simultaneous solutions of Equations (4) and (5) in certain cases (see [6]).

Proposition 2 (Unsolvability Condition). *Let*

$$n = 2^\epsilon r_1 r_2 \cdots r_k$$

be a square-free positive integer where $\epsilon \in \{0, 1\}$, k is a natural number, and r_1, r_2, \dots, r_k are odd primes. Let $(b_1, b_2) \in R \times R$, where R is as defined in Remark 1. The system of equations given by (4) and (5) has no solution $(z_1, z_2, z_3) \in \mathbb{Q}^ \times \mathbb{Q}^* \times \mathbb{Q}^*$ in the following cases:*

- (a) $b_1b_2 < 0$ or
- (b) $2 \nmid n$ and $2 \mid b_1$.

It is convenient for us to express the unsolvability condition in terms of integral solutions rather than rational solutions as follows.

Lemma 1. *Let $(z_1, z_2, z_3) \in (\mathbb{Q}^*)^3$ be a solution to Equations (4) and (5). Then there exist a positive integer d and pairwise coprime integers a_1, a_2 and a_3 such that*

$$z_1 = \frac{a_1}{d}, \quad z_2 = \frac{a_2}{d}, \quad z_3 = \frac{a_3}{d}, \quad \text{and } (a_i, d) = 1.$$

Proof. We write $z_i = \frac{a_i}{d_i}$ for $i = 1, 2, 3$ as fractions in irreducible form with $d_i > 0$. After clearing denominators, Equation (4) becomes

$$b_1a_1^2d_2^2 - b_2a_2^2d_1^2 = nd_1^2d_2^2. \tag{7}$$

By simple inspection, we can say that $d_1^2|b_1d_2^2$ and $d_2^2|b_2d_1^2$. Since b_1 and b_2 are square-free, we must have $d_1|d_2$ and $d_2|d_1$, hence $d_1 = d_2$. We set $d := d_1 = d_2$. Now, after clearing denominators, Equation (5) becomes

$$b_1a_1^2d_3^2 - b_1b_2a_3^2d^2 = -nd^2d_3^2. \tag{8}$$

It is easy to see $d^2|b_1d_3^2$ and since b_1 is square-free, $d|d_3$. Thus we write $d_3 = md$. By dividing both sides by d^2 in Equation (8), we get

$$b_1a_1^2m^2 - b_1b_2a_3^2 = -nd^2m^2. \tag{9}$$

Equation (9) gives us $m^2|b_1b_2$, and since b_1 and b_2 are square-free, we have $m|b_1$ and $m|b_2$, and m is also square-free. Our target is to show $m = 1$. It can be shown that $(m, nd) = 1$. Suppose p is a prime dividing (m, nd) , then $\nu_p(b_1a_1^2m^2) \geq 3$ and $\nu_p(b_1b_2a_3^2) = 2$ but $\nu_p(nm^2d^2) \geq 3$, a contradiction to Equation (8). Now since $b_i \equiv 0 \pmod{m}$ for $i = 1, 2$, from Equation (7) we get $m = 1$, hence $d_3 = d$.

Now, we can rewrite (4) and (5) as

$$b_1a_1^2 - b_2a_2^2 = nd^2, \tag{10}$$

$$b_1a_1^2 - b_1b_2a_3^2 = -nd^2. \tag{11}$$

By taking the sum and the difference of the pair of equations above, we further obtain

$$2b_1a_1^2 - b_2a_2^2 - b_1b_2a_3^2 = 0, \tag{12}$$

$$b_2a_2^2 - b_1b_2a_3^2 = -2nd^2. \tag{13}$$

Since n is square-free and $(a_i, d) = 1$ for $i = 1, 2, 3$, we can easily deduce from above that $(a_1, a_2) = (a_1, a_3) = (a_2, a_3) = 1$. □

Corollary 1. *If $(b_1, b_2) \in \mathbb{Q}(S, 2) \times \mathbb{Q}(S, 2) \setminus \text{Im}\{\mathcal{O}, (0, 0), (\pm n, 0)\}$ then $(b_1, b_2) \in \text{Im}(b)$ if and only if there exist pairwise coprime integers a_1, a_2, a_3 and d satisfying the system of equations (10) and (11), or equivalently, (12) and (13).*

3. Proof of Theorem 1

In order to prove that $n = (p_1q_1)(p_2q_2) \cdots (p_tq_t)$ is a non-congruent number as stated in Theorem 1, we need to use the Legendre symbols listed as follows.

Remark 2. (a) Suppose $n = n'_jq_j = n''_jp_j$ for all $j \in \{1, 2, \dots, t\}$. Then

$$\left(\frac{n'_j}{q_j}\right) = (-1)^j, \quad \text{and} \quad \left(\frac{n''_j}{p_j}\right) = -1. \tag{14}$$

Moreover,

$$\left(\frac{q_j}{q_i}\right) = -1 \quad \text{for } i > j \text{ implies } \left(\frac{q_j}{q_i}\right) = 1 \quad \text{for } j > i. \tag{15}$$

(b) When all the prime pairs in the factorization of n in Theorem 1 satisfy $(p_j, q_j) \equiv (5, 7) \pmod{8}$, we have

$$\left(\frac{-1}{p_j}\right) = -\left(\frac{2}{p_j}\right) = 1, \quad \left(\frac{-1}{q_j}\right) = -\left(\frac{2}{q_j}\right) = -1. \tag{16}$$

(c) When all the prime pairs in the factorization of n in Theorem 1 satisfy $(p_j, q_j) \equiv (1, 3) \pmod{8}$, we have

$$\left(\frac{-1}{p_j}\right) = \left(\frac{2}{p_j}\right) = 1, \quad \left(\frac{-1}{q_j}\right) = \left(\frac{2}{q_j}\right) = -1. \tag{17}$$

By Corollary 1, it suffices to show that the system of equations (10) and (11) or equivalently, (12) and (13), cannot simultaneously be solved for any pair

$$(b_1, b_2) \in D := R \times R \setminus \{(1, 1), (-1, -n), (n, 2), (-n, -2n)\}, \tag{18}$$

with $R = \{\pm 2^\epsilon p_1^{\epsilon_1} \cdots p_t^{\epsilon_t} q_1^{\mu_1} \cdots q_t^{\mu_t} \mid \epsilon, \epsilon_1, \dots, \epsilon_t, \mu_1, \dots, \mu_t \in \{0, 1\}\}$.

By Proposition 2, we know that the equivalent system of equations (4) and (5) do not have a solution when $b_1 b_2 < 0$, or when $2 \nmid n$ and $2 \mid b_1$. Therefore, we only need to consider pairs (b_1, b_2) for which $b_1 b_2 > 0$ and $2 \nmid b_1$. The following lemma shows that it is enough to consider pairs (b_1, b_2) for which b_2 is positive and odd.

Lemma 2. *Let $(b_1, b_2) \in D$ represent an element in the image of the map b given by (3). Then, there is a pair (b_1^*, b_2^*) in D representing an element in $Im(b)$ such that b_2^* is positive and odd.*

Proof. Let us first assume that b_2 is positive and even. Then the set of points

$$L = \{(1, 1), (-1, -n), (n, 2), (-n, -2n), (b_1, b_2)\}$$

generates a subgroup of $Im(b)$ inside $\mathbb{Q}(S, 2) \times \mathbb{Q}(S, 2)$. By closure, the pair

$$(b_1, b_2) \cdot (n, 2) = (nb_1, 2b_2) \in Im(b).$$

By our assumption $2 \mid b_2$, hence we can write $2b_2 = 2^2 b_2^*$, where $b_2^* \in \mathbb{Q}/(\mathbb{Q}^*)^2$ and $2 \nmid b_2^*$. If we set $b_1^* = nb_1$, then we have

$$(nb_1, 2b_2) = (b_1^*, b_2^*) \in Im(b) \subset \mathbb{Q}(S, 2) \times \mathbb{Q}(S, 2),$$

where b_2^* is odd.

Next, let us assume that b_2 is negative and odd. As before, we have

$$(b_1, b_2) \cdot (-n, -2n) = (-nb_1, -2b_2n) = (b_1^*, b_2^*) \in Im(b),$$

where $b_2^* = -2b_2n$ is positive and even. But it leads us to the previous case.

Finally, let b_2 be negative and even. Then the pair

$$(b_1, b_2) \cdot (-n, -2n) = (-b_1n, -2b_2n) \in Im(b)$$

as well. Equivalently, the pair

$$(b_1^*, b_2^*) \in Im(b) \subset \mathbb{Q}(S, 2) \times \mathbb{Q}(S, 2),$$

where $b_1^* = -b_1n, -2b_2n = 2^2b_2^*$ with b_2^* as positive and odd. □

By Corollary 1, (18) and Lemma 2, it now suffices to show that for a pair (b_1, b_2) in D with b_2 positive and odd, the system of equations (10), (11) has a solution only when $(b_1, b_2) = (1, 1)$. Since b_1, b_2 are factors of n , we next show that none of the q_j divides b_1b_2 in Lemma 3 and that none of the p_j divides b_1b_2 in Lemma 4. We extend the argument employed by Iskra in [2] that dealt with the case when n has all its prime factors in the form $8k + 3$.

Lemma 3. *Let (b_1, b_2) be an element of $R \times R$ such that b_2 is odd and positive. If $(b_1, b_2) \in Im(b)$, then q_j does not divide b_1b_2 for $j = 1, 2, \dots, t$.*

Proof. We provide the argument when all pairs $(p_j, q_j) \equiv (5, 7) \pmod{8}$. The proof is similar when all pairs $(p_j, q_j) \equiv (1, 3) \pmod{8}$. Define

$$U = \{j : q_j|b_1 \text{ or } q_j|b_2\}.$$

It is enough to show that U is the empty set. Suppose otherwise, and let u be the least element of U . Let

$$b'_i = \begin{cases} \frac{b_i}{q_u}, & \text{if } q_u|b_i \\ b_i, & \text{if } q_u \nmid b_i \end{cases} \quad \text{and} \quad b''_i = \begin{cases} \frac{b_i}{p_u}, & \text{if } p_u|b_i \\ b_i, & \text{if } p_u \nmid b_i \end{cases} \quad i = 1 \text{ or } 2.$$

By Remark 2,

$$\left(\frac{b'_i}{q_u}\right) = \begin{cases} -1, & \text{if } p_u|b_i \\ 1, & \text{if } p_u \nmid b_i, \end{cases} \quad \text{for } i = 1, 2. \tag{19}$$

According to the definition of u , q_u divides both b_1 and b_2 or exactly one of them. We consider these three cases separately.

Case 1: $q_u|b_1$ and $q_u|b_2$. We have the following possibilities.

Subcase I: $p_u \nmid b_1$ and $p_u \nmid b_2$. From Equation (11) we obtain $b_1a_1^2 - b_1b_2a_3^2 \equiv 0 \pmod{p_u}$, i.e.,

$$a_1^2 \equiv b_2a_3^2 \pmod{p_u}.$$

As $(a_1, a_3) = 1$, we have $\left(\frac{b_2}{p_u}\right) = 1$. But it is not possible, since q_u is a divisor of b_2 .

Subcase II: $p_u \mid b_1$ and $p_u \mid b_2$. Dividing both side of Equation (13) by p_u , we obtain $b_2''a_2^2 - b_1b_2''a_3^2 = -2n_u''d^2$, i.e.,

$$b_2''a_2^2 \equiv -2n_u''d^2 \pmod{p_u}.$$

Since $(a_2, d) = 1$, we have $\left(\frac{-2n_u''b_2''}{p_u}\right) = 1$. Consequently, $\left(\frac{b_2''}{p_u}\right) = 1$. It is not possible, since q_u is a divisor of b_2'' .

Subcase III: $p_u \mid b_1$ but $p_u \nmid b_2$. In this case,

$$\left(\frac{b_2'}{q_u}\right) = -\left(\frac{b_1'}{q_u}\right) = 1.$$

Dividing both sides of Equation (11) by q_u , we obtain $b_1'a_1^2 - b_1'b_2a_3^2 = -n_u'd^2$. Hence,

$$b_1'a_1^2 \equiv -n_u'd^2 \pmod{q_u}.$$

Since $(a_1, d) = 1$, we have $\left(\frac{-n_u'b_1'}{q_u}\right) = \left(\frac{-1}{q_u}\right)\left(\frac{n_u'}{q_u}\right)\left(\frac{b_1'}{q_u}\right) = 1$. It follows that

$$\left(\frac{n_u'}{q_u}\right) = 1. \tag{20}$$

On the other hand, division of both sides of (13) by q_u yields $b_2'a_2^2 - b_1b_2'a_3^2 = -2n_u'd^2$. Hence,

$$b_2'a_2^2 \equiv -2n_u'd^2 \pmod{q_u}.$$

As $(a_2, d) = 1$, we have $\left(\frac{-2n_u'b_2'}{q_u}\right) = \left(\frac{-1}{q_u}\right)\left(\frac{2}{q_u}\right)\left(\frac{b_2'}{q_u}\right)\left(\frac{n_u'}{q_u}\right) = 1$. It follows that $\left(\frac{n_u'}{q_u}\right) = -1$, which contradicts (20).

Subcase IV: $p_u \nmid b_1$ and $p_u \mid b_2$. This case can be ruled out in a similar way as above.

Case 2: $q_u \mid b_1$ and $q_u \nmid b_2$. As before, we consider the following subcases.

Subcase I: $p_u \nmid b_1$ and $p_u \nmid b_2$. From Equation (10) we have

$$b_1a_1^2 \equiv b_2a_2^2 \pmod{p_u}.$$

Since $(a_1, a_2) = 1$, we have $\left(\frac{b_1b_2}{p_u}\right) = 1$, which is impossible, since $q_u \mid b_1$ but not b_2 .

Subcase II: $p_u \mid b_1$ and $p_u \mid b_2$. Equation (10) gives us $b_2a_2^2 \equiv 0 \pmod{q_u}$. It follows that a_2 is divisible by q_u , and $\frac{a_2^2}{q_u}$ is divisible by q_u . Dividing both sides of Equation (12) by q_u , we obtain $2b_1'a_1^2 - b_2\frac{a_2^2}{q_u} - b_1'b_2a_3^2 = 0$ and consequently,

$$2a_1^2 \equiv b_2a_3^2 \pmod{q_u}.$$

Now, $(a_1, a_3) = 1$ implies $\left(\frac{2b_2}{q_u}\right) = 1$, which is a contradiction since p_u divides b_2 .

Subcase III: $p_u | b_1$ and $p_u \nmid b_2$. Equation (10) gives us a_2 is divisible by p_u . Now dividing both sides of Equation (13) by p_u , we obtain $b_2 \frac{a_2^2}{p_u} - b_1'' b_2 a_3^2 = -2n_u'' d^2$, i.e.,

$$b_1'' b_2 a_3^2 \equiv 2n_u'' d^2 \pmod{p_u}. \tag{21}$$

Since $(a_3, d) = 1$, it follows that $\left(\frac{2n_u'' b_1'' b_2}{p_u}\right) = 1$. But

$$\left(\frac{2n_u'' b_1'' b_2}{p_u}\right) = \left(\frac{2}{p_u}\right) \left(\frac{n_u''}{p_u}\right) \left(\frac{b_1''}{p_u}\right) \left(\frac{b_2}{p_u}\right) = (-1) \cdot (-1) \cdot (-1) \cdot 1 = -1,$$

a contradiction to (21).

Subcase IV: $p_u \nmid b_1$ and $p_u | b_2$. The argument is similar to the previous one.

Case 3: $q_u \nmid b_1$ and $q_u | b_2$. We consider following subcases.

Subcase I: $p_u \nmid b_1$. Equation (10) gives us $b_1 a_1^2 \equiv 0 \pmod{q_u}$. It follows that a_1 is divisible by q_u , and $\frac{a_1^2}{q_u}$ is divisible by q_u . Dividing both sides of Equation (12) by q_u , we obtain $2b_1 \frac{a_1^2}{q_u} - b_2' a_2^2 - b_1 b_2' a_3^2 = 0$ and consequently,

$$a_2^2 \equiv -b_1 a_3^2 \pmod{q_u}.$$

Now, $(a_2, a_3) = 1$ implies $\left(\frac{-b_1}{q_u}\right) = 1$, which is a contradiction because p_u does not divide b_1 .

Subcase II: $p_u | b_1$ and $p_u | b_2$. From Equation (11) we have

$$b_1'' a_1^2 \equiv -n_u'' d^2 \pmod{p_u}.$$

Since $(a_1, d) = 1$, we have $\left(\frac{-n_u'' b_1''}{p_u}\right) = 1$, which is impossible since $q_u \nmid b_1$.

Subcase III: $p_u | b_1$ and $p_u \nmid b_2$. Equation (10) gives us a_2 is divisible by p_u . Dividing both sides of Equation (10) by p_u , we obtain $b_1'' a_1^2 - b_2 \frac{a_2^2}{p_u} = n_u'' d^2$. Clearly,

$$b_1'' a_1^2 \equiv n_u'' d^2 \pmod{p_u}. \tag{22}$$

Since $(a_1, d) = 1$, $\left(\frac{n_u'' b_1''}{p_u}\right) = 1$. But

$$\left(\frac{n_u'' b_1''}{p_u}\right) = \left(\frac{n_u''}{p_u}\right) \left(\frac{b_1''}{p_u}\right) = (-1) \cdot 1 = -1,$$

a contradiction to (22).

Therefore, we can conclude that $u = \min U$ does not exist, i.e., U is empty. So, none of the prime factors q_j of n divides $b_1 b_2$. \square

Lemma 4. *Let (b_1, b_2) be an element of $R \times R$ such that b_2 is odd and positive. If $(b_1, b_2) \in \text{Im}(b)$, then p_j does not divide $b_1 b_2$ for $j = 1, 2, \dots, t$.*

Proof. We provide the argument when all prime pairs in the factorization of n satisfy $(p_j, q_j) \equiv (5, 7) \pmod{8}$. The proof is similar when all pairs $(p_j, q_j) \equiv (1, 3) \pmod{8}$. Let us define

$$V = \{j : p_j | b_1 \text{ or } p_j | b_2\}.$$

It suffices to show that V is empty. If possible, let V be non-empty and v be the least element of V . Let

$$b_{i,v} = \begin{cases} \frac{b_i}{p_v}, & \text{if } p_v | b_i \\ b_i, & \text{if } p_v \nmid b_i \end{cases} \quad i = 1, 2.$$

Since $q_j \nmid b_1 b_2$, for all $j \in \{1, 2, \dots, t\}$, we have

$$\left(\frac{b_{1,v}}{p_v}\right) = \left(\frac{b_{2,v}}{p_v}\right) = 1.$$

We need to consider the following three cases.

Case A: $p_v | b_1$ and $p_v | b_2$. Dividing Equation (11) by p_v , we have $b_{1,v} a_1^2 - b_{1,v} b_2 a_3^2 = -n''_v d^2$. Clearly,

$$b_{1,v} a_1^2 \equiv -n''_v d^2 \pmod{p_v}.$$

Since $(a_1, d) = 1$, we have $\left(\frac{-n''_v b_{1,v}}{p_v}\right) = 1$. It follows that $\left(\frac{n''_v}{p_v}\right) = 1$, a contradiction to (14).

Case B: $p_v | b_1$ and $p_v \nmid b_2$. From Equation (10) we have $a_2 \equiv 0 \pmod{p_v}$. Therefore, $b_{1,v} a_1^2 - b_2 \frac{a_2^2}{p_v} = n''_v d^2$, and

$$b_{1,v} a_1^2 \equiv n''_v d^2 \pmod{p_v}.$$

Since $(a_1, d) = 1$, we have $\left(\frac{n''_v b_{1,v}}{p_v}\right) = 1$. It follows that $\left(\frac{n''_v}{p_v}\right) = 1$, a contradiction to (14).

Case C: $p_v \nmid b_1$ and $p_v | b_2$. From Equation (10) we have $a_1 \equiv 0$ in modulo p_v . Therefore, $b_1 \frac{a_1^2}{p_v} - b_{2,v} a_2^2 = n''_v d^2$ and

$$-b_{2,v} a_2^2 \equiv n''_v d^2 \pmod{p_v}.$$

Since $(a_2, d) = 1$, we have $\left(\frac{-n''_v b_{2,v}}{p_v}\right) = 1$. But it implies that $\left(\frac{n''_v}{p_v}\right) = 1$, a contradiction to (14). □

By Lemmas 3 and 4, we can conclude that if $(b_1, b_2) \in Im(b)$ with $b_1 b_2 > 0$ and b_2 odd as well as positive, then $b_2 = 1 = b_1$. Hence, Theorem 1 follows from Propositions 1 and 2, and Corollary 1.

4. Infinitude of the Families

In this section, we show that Theorem 1 provides infinitely many families of non-congruent numbers and each family has infinitely many members by proving Theorem 2.

Proof of Theorem 2. We use Dirichlet’s theorem on primes in arithmetic progression and apply induction on t . The case when $t = 1$ is trivial, since we can take any $q_1 \equiv 3 \pmod{8}$ and $p_1 \equiv 1 \pmod{8}$, $p_1 \equiv 2 \pmod{q_1}$. Suppose $t > 1$. By the induction hypothesis, we know that there exists an integer $n_{t-1} = (p_1q_1)(p_2q_2) \cdots (p_{t-1}q_{t-1})$ where p_1, p_2, \dots, p_{t-1} and q_1, q_2, \dots, q_{t-1} are distinct primes such that $p_j \equiv 1 \pmod{8}$ and $q_j \equiv 3 \pmod{8}$ for all $1 \leq j \leq t - 1$ satisfying (2).

It is enough if we can choose primes p_t and q_t satisfying

$$q_t \equiv \begin{cases} 3 & \pmod{8}, \\ \alpha & \pmod{n_{t-1}}, \end{cases} \tag{23}$$

and

$$p_t \equiv \begin{cases} 1 & \pmod{8}, \\ \beta & \pmod{n_{t-1}}, \\ \gamma & \pmod{q_t}, \end{cases} \tag{24}$$

where α, β is any quadratic residue modulo n_{t-1} and γ is any quadratic non-residue modulo q_t , e.g., $\alpha = 1 = \beta, \gamma = 2$. The Chinese Remainder Theorem guarantees that both the systems of congruences (23) and (24) have a solution. By applying this theorem in conjunction with Dirichlet’s theorem on primes in arithmetic progression and quadratic reciprocity, we can conclude that there exist infinitely many primes p_t and q_t satisfying the system of congruences given by (24) and (23), respectively.

The analogous statement, when all the prime pairs (p_j, q_j) in the factorization of n are equivalent to $(5, 7)$ modulo 8, can be proved similarly. \square

5. Examples

Example 1. Consider $n = (17 \cdot 3) \cdot (409 \cdot 19) \cdot (3697 \cdot 859)$, where each pair of prime factors is equivalent to $(1, 3)$ modulo 8 and satisfy the hypotheses (2) of Theorem 1. Using MAGMA [1], we verify that the rank of the elliptic curve $y^2 = x^3 - n^2x$ is 0, hence n is non-congruent. We further verify that $(17 \cdot 3) \cdot (409 \cdot 19)$, $(17 \cdot 3) \cdot (3697 \cdot 859)$ and $(409 \cdot 19) \cdot (3697 \cdot 859)$ are non-congruent too, as implied by Theorem 1.

Example 2. Consider $n = (5 \cdot 7) \cdot (29 \cdot 79) \cdot (821 \cdot 151)$ where each pair of prime factors is equivalent to $(5, 7)$ modulo 8 and satisfy the hypotheses (2) of Theorem 1. Using MAGMA [1], we verify that the rank of the elliptic curve $y^2 = x^3 - n^2x$ is 0,

hence n is non-congruent. We further verify that $(5 \cdot 7) \cdot (29 \cdot 79)$, $(5 \cdot 7) \cdot (821 \cdot 151)$ and $(29 \cdot 79) \cdot (821 \cdot 151)$ are non-congruent too, as implied by Theorem 1.

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